

PERFORMANCE AND ANALYSIS OF LOW POWER, AREA EFFICIENT AND HIGH SPEED CARRYFAST ADDER

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Abstract- Carry Select Adder (CSLA) is one of the fastest adders used in many data-processing processors to perform fast arithmetic functions. From the structure of the CSLA, it is clear that there is scope for reducing the area and power consumption in the CSLA. This work uses a simple and efficient gate-level modification to significantly reduce the area and power of the CSLA. Based on this modification 8, 16,32,and 64-bit square-root CSLA (SQRT CSLA) architecture have been developed and compared with the regular SQRT CSLA architecture. The proposed design has reduced area and power as compared with the regular SQRT CSLA with only a slight increase in the delay. This work evaluates the performance of the proposed designs in terms of delay, area, power. Binary to Excess-1 Converter (BEC) instead of RCA with the regular CSLA to achieve lower area and power consumption. The main advantage of this BEC logic comes from the lesser number of logic gates than the n-bit Full Adder structure. The delay and area evaluation methodology of the basic adder blocks. The SQRT CSLA has been chosen for comparison with the proposed design as it has a more balanced delay, and requires lower power and area. Reducing the area and power consumption in the CSLA. Efficient gate-level modification to significantly reduce the area and power of the CSLA.

Index terms: Carry Select Adder (CSLA), Binary to Excess-1 Converter (BEC), Carry-propagation adder (CPA)

I. INTRODUCTION

High-speed data path logic systems are one of the most substantial areas of research in VLSI system design. The speed of addition is limited by the time required to propagate a carry through the adder in digital adders. The sum for each bit position in an elementary adder is generated sequentially only after the previous bit position has been summed and a carry propagated into the next position. The CSLA is used in many computational systems to alleviate the problem of carry propagation delay by independently generating multiple carries and then select a carry to generate the sum the CSLA is not area efficient because it uses multiple pairs of Ripple Carry Adders (RCA) to generate partial sum and carry. Design of high speed data path logic systems are one of the most substantial research area in VLSI system design. High-speed addition and multiplication has always been a fundamental requirement of high-performance processors and systems. The major speed limitation in any adder is in the production of carries and many authors have considered the addition problem. The basic idea of the proposed work is using n-bit binary to excess-1 code converters (BEC) to improve the speed of addition. The detailed structure and function of BEC . This logic can be implemented with any type of adder to further improve the speed. The proposed 16, 32 and 64-bit adders are compared in this paper with the conventional fast adders such as carry save adder (CSA) and carry look ahead adder (CLA). This paper has realized the improved performance of the CSA with BEC logic through custom design and layout The final stage CPA constitutes a dominant component of the delay in the parallel multiplier. Signals from the multiplier partial products summation tree do not arrive at the final CPA at the same time. This is due to the fact that the number of partial-product bits is larger in the middle of the multiplier tree. Due to un-even arrival time of the input signals to the final CPA, the selection of the ASIC Implementation of Modified Faster Carry Save Adder 54 final adder is an important work in parallel multipliers . Therefore decrease in carry propagation delay will result in major enhancement of the speed of the adder and multiplier. An overview of the 4-bit binary to excess-1 logic is provided.It deals with the proposed modified carry save adder (MCSA) architecture. Among the myriad of aggressive techniques, carry select adder (CSL) has been an eminent technique in the space-time tug-of-war of CPA design. It exhibits the advantage of logarithmic gate depth as in any structure of the distant-carry adder family. Conventionally, CSL is implemented with dual ripple-carry adder (RCA) with the carry-in of 0 and 1, respectively. Depending on the configuration of block length, CSL is further classified as either linear or

square root. The basic idea of CSL is anticipatory parallel computation. Although it can achieve high speed by not waiting for the carry-in from previous sub-block before computation can begin, they consume more power due to doubling the amount of circuitry needed to do the parallel addition of which half of the speculative computations will be redundant.. Digital Adders are the core block of DSP processors. The final carry propagation adder (CPA) structure of many adders constitutes high carry propagation delay and this delay reduces the overall performance of the DSP processor. This paper proposes a simple and efficient approach to reduce the maximum delay of carry propagation in the final stage. Based on this approach a 16, 32 and 64-bit adder architecture has been developed and compared with conventional fast adder architectures. This work identifies the performance of proposed designs in terms of delay-area-power through custom design and layout in process technology. The result analysis shows that the proposed architectures have better performance in reduction of carry propagation delay than contemporary architectures. The number of bits in each carry select block can be uniform, or variable. In the uniform case, the optimal delay occurs for a block size of \sqrt{n} . When variable, the block size should have a delay, from addition inputs A and B to the carry out, equal to that of the multiplexer chain leading into it, so that the carry out is calculated just in time. The delay is derived from uniform sizing, where the ideal number of full-adder elements per block is equal to the square root of the number of bits being added, since that will yield an equal number of MUX delays. In digital adders, the speed of addition is limited by the time required to propagate a carry through the adder.

The sum for each bit position in an elementary adder is generated sequentially only after the previous bit position has been summed and a carry propagated into the next position. The CSLA is used in many computational systems to alleviate the problem of carry propagation delay by independently generating multiple carries and then select a carry to generate the sum in reference1. However, the CSLA is not area efficient because it uses multiple pairs of Ripple Carry Adders (RCA) to generate partial sum and carry by considering carry input $C_{in}=0$ and $C_{in}=1$, then the final sum and carry are selected by the multiplexers (MUX). The basic idea of this work is to use Binary to Excess- 1 converter (BEC) instead of RCA with $C_{in} = 1$ in the regular CSLA to achieve lower area and power consumption in ref 2–4. The main advantage of this BEC logic comes from the lesser number of logic gates than the n-bit Full Adder (FA) structure. The details of the BEC logic are discussed. Carry-ripple adder (CRA) is the simplest approach.

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However, the carry-look ahead adder (CLA) and its fast version, the parallel-prefix CLA, is the selected scheme for time-critical applications with a considerable cost in terms of silicon area and power dissipation. The CSA provides a compromise between a RCA and a CLA adder. Due to rapidly growing system-on-chip industry, not only the faster units but also smaller area and less power has become a major concern for designing very large scale integration (VLSI) circuits. Digital circuits make use of digital arithmetic's. Among various arithmetic operations, multiplication is one of the fundamental operation used and is being performed by an adder. There are many ways to build a multiplier each providing trade-off between delays and other characteristics, such as area and energy dissipation. However no design is considered as superior. Carry-Save based Multiplier is one of the promising techniques in terms of speed. It provides a compromise between ripple carry adder and carry look-ahead adder, but to a lesser extent at the cost of its area.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

High-speed addition and multiplication has always been a fundamental requirement of high-performance processors and systems. The major speed limitation in any adder is in the production of carries and many authors have considered the addition problem. High-speed data path logic systems are one of the most substantial areas of research in VLSI system design. The speed of addition is limited by the time required to propagate a carry through the adder in digital adders. More power consumption[1]. Digital Adders are the core block of DSP processors. The final carry propagation adder (CPA) structure of many adders constitutes high carry propagation delay and this delay reduces the overall performance of the DSP processor. This paper proposes a simple and efficient approach to reduce the maximum delay of carry propagation in the final stage. Based on this approach a 16, 32 and 64-bit adder architecture has been developed and compared with conventional fast adder architectures. This work identifies the performance of proposed designs in terms of delay-area-power through custom design[2]. A carry-select adder can be implemented by using single ripple carry adder and an add-one circuit instead of using dual ripple-carry adders. This paper proposes a new add-one circuit using the first zero finding circuit and multiplexers to reduce the area and power with no speed penalty. For bit length $n = 64$, this new carry-select adder requires fewer transistors than the dual ripple-carry carry-select adder and fewer transistors than Chang's carry-select adder using single ripple carry adder[3,7]. In this ,Carry-select method has deemed to be a good compromise between cost and performance in

carry propagation adder design. However, conventional carry-select adder (CSL) is still area-consuming due to the dual ripple carry adder structure. The excessive area overhead makes CSL relatively unattractive but this has been circumvented by the use of add-one circuit introduced recently. In this paper, an area efficient square root CSL scheme based on a new first zero detection logic is proposed. The proposed CSL witnesses a notable power-delay and area-delay performance improvement by virtue of proper exploitation of logic structure and circuit technique[4,5,6].

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A structure of 4-bit BEC and the truth table is shown. How the goal of fast addition is achieved using BEC together with a multiplexer (mux) is described , one input of the 8:4 mux gets as it input (B3, B2, B1, and B0) and another input of the mux is the BEC output. This produces the two possible partial product results in parallel and the muxes are used to select either BEC output or the direct inputs according to the control signal Cin.

The Boolean expressions of 4-bit BEC are listed below, (Note: functional symbols, ~ NOT, & AND, ^ XOR).

$$X0 = \sim B0 \quad (1)$$

$$X1 = B0 \wedge B1 \quad (2)$$

$$X2 = B2 \wedge (B0 \& B1) \quad (3)$$

$$X3 = B3 \wedge (B0 \& B1 \& B2)$$

XOR GATE MODEL

Fig - 1 XOR gate model

Today, one of the major challenges for high-performance microelectronic systems is the power dissipation, both static and dynamic. The circuit designer must, therefore, find an optimum

Performance and analysis of low power, area efficient and high speed carryfast adder between power and speed, instead of targeting them independently, and this is represented by the power-delay product, which represents the average energy dissipated for one switching event. Due to the rapidly growing mobile industry, not only faster arithmetic units but also smaller and lower power arithmetic units are demanded. However, it has been difficult to do well both in speed and in area. Ripple-carry adder (RCA) provides a compact design but suffers from a long delay time. Carry look ahead adder (CLA) gives a fast design but has a large area. Carry-select adder (CSA) is intermediate in regard to speed and area. Addition is by far the most fundamental arithmetic operation. It has been ranked the most extensively used operation among a set of real-time digital signal processing benchmarks from application-specific DSP to general purpose processors. Carry-propagation adder (CPA) is frequently part of the critical delay path limiting the overall system performance due to the inevitable carry propagation chain. The increase in the popularity of portable systems as well as the rapid growth of the power density in integrated circuits have made power dissipation one of the important design objectives, second only to performance shown in fig 1..

The carry select adder generally consists of two ripple carry adders and a multiplexer. Adding two n-bit numbers with a carry select adder is done with two adders (therefore two ripple carry adders) in order to perform the calculation twice, one time with the assumption of the carry being zero and the other assuming one. After the two results are calculated, the correct sum, as well as the correct carry, is then selected with the multiplexer once the correct carry is known. The carry select adder partitions the adder into several groups, each of which performs two additions in parallel. Therefore, two copies of ripple-carry adder act as carry evaluation block per select stage. One copy evaluates the array chain assuming the block carry-in is zero, while the other assumes it to be one. The conventional n-bit CSA consists of one n/2-bit adder for the lower half of the bits and two n/2-bit adders for the upper half of the bits. Of the two latter adders, one performs the addition with the assumption that $C_{in}=0$, whereas the other does this with the assumption that $C_{in}=1$. Using a multiplexer and the value of carry out that is propagated from the adder for the n/2 least significant bits, the correct value of the most significant part of the addition can be selected. Although this technique has the drawback of increasing the area, it speeds up the addition operation.

A 16-bit carry select adder with a uniform block size of 4 can be created with three of these blocks and a 4-bit ripple carry adder. Since carry-in is known at the beginning of computation, a

carry select block is not needed for the first four bits. The delay of this adder will be four full adder delays, plus three MUX delays. Two 4-bit ripple carry adders are multiplexed together, where the resulting carry and sum bits are selected by the carry-in. Since one ripple carry adder assumes a carry-in of 0, and the other assumes a carry-in of 1, selecting which adder had the correct assumption via the actual carry-in yields the desired result. The carry select adder comes in the category of conditional sum adder. Conditional sum adder works on some condition. Sum and carry are calculated by assuming input carry as 1 and 0 prior the input carry comes. When actual carry input arrives, the actual calculated values of sum and carry are selected using a multiplexer.

The conventional carry select adder consists of $k/2$ bit adder for the lower half of the bits i.e. least significant bits and for the upper half i.e. most significant bits (MSB's) two $k/2$ bit adders. In MSB adders one adder assumes carry input as one for performing addition and another assumes carry input as zero. The carry out calculated from the last stage i.e. least significant bit stage is used to select the actual calculated values of output carry and sum. The selection is done by using a multiplexer. This technique of dividing adder in to stages increases the area utilization but addition operation fastens.

IV. METHODOLOGIES

The availability of a large variety of codes for the same discrete elements of information results in the use of different codes by different digital systems. It is sometimes necessary to use the output of one system as the input to another. A conversion circuit must be inserted between the two systems if each uses different codes for the same information. Thus, a code converter is a circuit that makes the two systems compatible even though each uses a different binary code shown in fig 2..

Fig.2 Block Diagram Of BCD To Excess 3 Code Converter

The bit combinations assigned to the BCD and excess-3 codes. Both BCD code and Excess 3 code use 4 bits to represent the numbers. But only 10 of 16 combinations are listed in the truth

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Table 1 TRUTH TABLE OF 4-BIT BINARY TO EXCESS-1

BINARY	EXCESS-1
0000	0001
0001	0010
0010	0011
0011	0100
0100	0101
0110	0110
0110	0111
0111	1000
1000	1001
1001	1010
1010	1011
1011	1100
1100	1101
1101	1110
1110	1111
1111	0000

4.1MODULE DESCRIPTION

The CSLA is used in many computational systems to alleviate the problem of carry propagation delay by independently generating multiple carries and then select a carry to generate the sum in reference 1. However, the CSLA is not area efficient because it uses multiple pairs of Ripple Carry Adders (RCA) to generate partial sum and carry by considering carry input $C_{in}=0$ and $C_{in}=1$, then the final sum and carry are selected by the multiplexers (mux). The basic idea of this work is to use Binary to Excess-1 converter (BEC) instead of RCA with $C_{in}=1$ in the regular CSLA to achieve lower area and power consumption. The main advantage of this BEC logic comes from

the lesser number of logic gates than the n-bit Full Adder (FA) structure. However, the carry-look ahead adder (CLA) and its fast version, the parallel-prefix CLA, is the selected scheme for time-critical applications with a considerable cost in terms of silicon area and power dissipation. The CSA provides a compromise between a RCA and a CLA adder. Hybrid adders combine elements of different approaches to obtain adders with a higher performance, reduced area and low power consumption.

Fig 3 REGULAR 16 BIT SQRT CSLA

In this module Half Adder is a digital combinational circuit that is used for the addition of two bits and provides an output in the form of a sum bit and a carry bit. The logical functional equations that relate the outputs S and C of a half adder circuit to the input bits are $Sum(S) = A \oplus B$, $Carry(C) = A \cdot B$. Thus a half adder circuit can easily be synthesized by using 1 X-OR gate and 1 AND gate. Since a half adder circuit can only be used to add two bits, it becomes obsolete in case of multi-bit addition in practical applications shown in fig 3..

4.2MODULE 2 MODULE

The basic idea of this work is to use Binary to Excess-1 Converter (BEC) instead of RCA with in the regular CSLA to achieve lower area and power consumption .The main advantage of this BEC logic comes from the lesser number of logic gates than the n-bit Full Adder (FA) structure.

Fig 4:GROUP 2 MODULE DIAGRAM

The main idea of this work is to use BEC instead of the RCA with in order to reduce the area and power consumption of the regular CSLA. To replace the n-bit RCA, an (n+1)-bit BEC is required. The group2 has two sets of 2-b RCA. Except for group2, the arrival time of mux selection input is always greater than the arrival time of data outputs from the RCA's. The one set of 2-b RCA in group2 has 2 FA for $C_{in}=1$ and the other set has 1 FA and 1 HA for $C_{in}=0$ shown in fig 4.

4.3GROUP 3 MODULE

The group3 has one 2-b RCA which has 1 FA and 1 HA for $C_{in}=0$. Instead of another 2-b RCA with $C_{in}=1$ a 3-b BEC is used which adds one to the output from 2-b RCA. Based on the consideration of delay values.The arrival time of selection input $C_3[\text{time}(t)=1]$ of 8:4 mux is earlier than the S_6 and C_6 and later than the S_4 . Thus, the sum_6 and final C_6 (output from mux) are depending on S_6 and mux and partial C_6 (input to mux) and mux, respectively. The sum_4 depends on C_3 and mux. In this module, We applied three input signal as mux_in and m. we obtain the output (specific signal) from given input signal. If A greater than B is equal to 1 will get mux_in signal. If A lesser than B we get m signal. Otherwise we get 0(8 bit signal) shown in fig 5.

Fig 5 GROUP 3 MODULE DIAGRAM

A data selector, more commonly called a **Multiplexer**, shortened to "Mux" or "MPX", are combinational logic switching devices that operate like a very fast acting multiple position rotary switch. They connect or control, multiple input lines called "channels" consisting of either 2, 4, 8 or 16 individual inputs, one at a time to an output. Then the job of a multiplexer is to allow multiple signals to *share* a single common output. For example, a single 8-channel multiplexer would connect one of its eight inputs to the single data output. Multiplexers are used as one method of reducing the number of logic gates required in a circuit or when a single data line is required to carry two or more different digital signals.

GROUP 4 MODULE

Fig 6 GROUP 4 MODULE DIAGRAM

The group4 has one 2-b RCA which has 1 FA and 1 HA for $C_{in}=0$. Instead of another 2-b RCA with $C_{in}=1$ a 3-b BEC is used which adds one to the output from 2-b RCA. Based on the consideration of delay values. The arrival time of selection input C_6 [time(t)=16] of 10:5 mux is earlier than the S_8 and C_{10} and later than the S_7 . Thus, the sum_8 and final C_{10} (output from

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4.4GROUP 5 MODULE

The group5 has one 2-b RCA which has 1 FA and 1 HA for Cin=0. Instead of another 2-b RCA with Cin=1 a 3-b BEC is used which adds one to the output from 2-b RCA. Based on the consideration of delay values . The arrival time of selection input C10[time(t)=19] of 12:6 mux is earlier than the S10 and Cout and later than the S11. Thus, the sum10 and final Cout (output from mux) are depending on S10 and mux and partial Cout(input to mux) and mux, respectively.

Fig 7 GROUP 5 MODULE DIAGRAM

A standard 8-bit ripple-carry adder built as a cascade from eight 1-bit full-adders. The input switches or use the following bind keys: ('c') for carry-in, for A0..A7 and B0..B7. To demonstrate the typical behavior of the ripple-carry adder, very large gate-delays are used for the gates inside the 1-bit adders - resulting in an addition time of about 0.6 seconds per adder. Note that each stage of the adder has to wait until the previous stage has calculated and propagates its carry output signal. Obviously, the longest delay results for operands like A = 0b00000000, B=0b11111111 or A=0b01010101 and B=0b10101010. Therefore, the total delay of a ripple-carry adder is proportional to the number of bits. Faster adders are often required for bit widths of 16 or greater shown in fig 7.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

Fig8:GROUP8MODULE

Fig 9:GROUP 3 MODULE

Fig10:GROUP4MODULE

Fig 11:GROUP 5 MODULE

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Fig 12:FINAL TOP OUTPUT

The implemented design in this work has been simulated using Verilog -HDL. The adders (of various size 16, 32, 64 and 128) are designed and simulated with Modelsim. All the V files (Regular and Modified) are also simulated in Modelsim and corresponding results are compared. After simulation the different size codes are synthesized using Xilinx ISE 9.1i. The simulated V files are imported into the synthesized tool and resultant values of delay and area are noted. The synthesized reports include area and delay values for different sized adders. The similar design flow is followed for both the regular and modified SQRT CSLA of different sizes are shown in fig 8-12

VI. CONCLUSION

All the adders designed are 32-bits wide. CSAS 5 stage consists of 5 stages with each block from LSB block to MSB blocks are [6-6-5-5-10] bits wide. These adders are faster than ripple carry adders but slower than carry select adders. All the adders are designed using VHDL (Very High Speed Integration Hardware Description Language), Xilinx Project Navigator 9.1i is used as a synthesis tool and ModelSim XE III 6.2g for simulation. FPGA Spartan3 is used for implementing the designs Gate count reduction is a sign of area reduction. Gate count of csas 2 stage is 11 less than carry select, 80 less than 3 stage carry select and 110 than 4 stage carry select adder. explore in this work is to design the adder in a way to reduce the delay as the area and power reduces. Wherever there is need of smaller area and low power consumption, while some

increase in delay is tolerated, such designs can be used. These adders are faster than RCA and slower than CSA.

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